

Reactions of Silicon Alkoxides with Aliphatic Acid Anhydrides

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Reactions of isopropoxy, butoxy¹, and amyl²oxy orthosilicates with acetic, propionic, and butyric anhydrides show that the reaction in 1:1 molar ratio affords the trialkoxy monoacylate derivatives, but in all cases a diacylate derivative is obtained as the end product when the reactants (the alkoxide and the acid anhydride) are taken in the molar ratio of 1:2 or in any other ratio greater than this.

Friedel and Crafts¹ reported that ethyl orthosilicate reacted with acetic anhydride to furnish tri-ethoxysilicomethyl acetate and the simple ester, thus :

Post and Hofrichter² further carried out the acylation of alkyl orthosilicates and showed that when equimolar proportions of the reactants were taken, not only were the mono-acylation products formed, but also the di-acylation products. They also carried out the reaction between ethyl orthosilicate and propionic anhydride³ and obtained tri-ethoxy monopropionate and di-ethoxy di-propionate of silicon. These workers did not pursue the reaction of other alkoxides with various acid anhydrides.

Some organo-silicon acetates have been prepared by using organo-silicon chloride with acetic anhydride and this seems to be the method most commonly used by Russian workers³.

In view of the meagre reference in the literature on the preparation of alkoxy-silicon acylates, it has been considered worthwhile to study the reaction between silicon alkoxides and various other acid anhydrides in different molar ratios.

The results obtained have been interesting. By taking various alkoxides (isopropoxide, butoxide¹, and amyl²oxide) and refluxing them with various acid anhydrides (acetic, propionic, and butyric), taken in different molar ratios in benzene which was then subsequently removed by distillation followed by distillation of the product in *vacuo*, various alkoxy acylates were obtained. In all these experiments the esters produced as a result of interaction were held up in a cold trap and were identified by their boiling point determinations. When the alkoxide and the acid anhydride are taken in equimolar ratios, the product is always a tri-alkoxysilicon monoacylate, but when the alkoxide and the acid anhydride ratio taken in or exceeded 1:2, 1:3, or 1:4, a di-alkoxysilicon di-acylate would result.

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1866 *iv*, 9, 10.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 443.

3. Andrianov *et al.*, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, S.S.S.R.* 1954, 94, 697; Dolgov *et al.*, *J. Gen. Chem.*, 1957, 27, 1593; Andrianov *et al.*, *ibid.*, p. 156.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with interchangeable joints was used throughout and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Fractionations were carried out in a column⁴ packed with Raschig rings and fitted to a total-condensation variable take-off stillhead.

The silicon alkoxides were prepared and purified by distillation under reduced pressure and their purity was confirmed by boiling points and analyses of silicon contents. The acid anhydrides used were E. Merck samples and freshly distilled. Benzene was dried by storage over sodium wire and finally dried azeotropically with ethanol over a long column.

• Silicon was estimated by digestion of the compound with a small amount of H_2SO_4 (conc.) followed by addition of a few drops of HNO_3 (conc.) and slowly ignition to dioxide.

The isopropoxide was estimated by oxidation of a small definite amount of the compound with $N-K_2Cr_2O_7$ (in 12.5% H_2SO_4) and after allowing it to stand for 2 hours at the room temperature, the unused chromic acid was titrated iodometrically⁴. Incidentally, very low analytical results were obtained by this method in isopropyl orthosilicate. It has been shown in a later publication⁵ that isopropyl orthosilicate or tri-isopropoxysilicon monoacylate are not hydrolysed to provide isopropanol and hence the analytical method is successful only in the cases of di-isopropoxysilicon di-acylate and monoisopropoxy-silicon tri-acylate.

The molecular weights were determined ebullioscopically in an inert dry organic solvent in a Gallencamp ebulliometer. The methods of preparation being similar, details are given for one preparation only.

Reaction between Silicon Isopropoxide and Propionic Anhydride (1:1).—Propionic anhydride (1.94 g.) was added to silicon isopropoxide (4.04 g.), taken in a 100 ml flask. No heat was evolved and no solid compound separated. To the above mixture was then added benzene (11.3 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4½ hrs. under a column (bath temp. 110–15°) and left overnight. No crystallisation was found to take place. Benzene was then removed over the column and its last traces were removed in a vacuum pump. To expel isopropyl propionate (b.p. 109–11°/750) the product was heated (35°–40°) under vacuum, when a slightly yellowish liquid (1.5 g.) accumulated in the cold trap. After 45 minutes bath temperature was raised to 100° when a colorless liquid (3.5 g.) slowly distilled at 56°/5 mm. [Found: Si, 9.98. $(OPr)_3Si(OOCEt)$ requires Si; 10.07%].

Reactions between Silicon Isopropoxide and Butyric Anhydride

(a). *In Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—Butyric anhydride (6.5 g.) was taken in a flask to which was added dry benzene (12.5 g.). Into this mixture was added silicon isopropoxide (10 g.). The whole was then refluxed under a column (bath temp. 110–15°) for 5 hrs. Benzene was distilled. After removal of isopropyl butyrate^a (b.p. 128°) at 35°/0.2 mm,

4. Mehrotra, *this Journal*, 1953, **30**, 585.

a colorless liquid (6.5 g.) slowly distilled at 74-75°/0.2mm. [Found: Si, 9.53. (OPr)₃-Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 9.59%]. After distillation about 1 g. of the liquid was left at bath 200°.

(b). *In Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—Benzene (12 g.) was added to butyric anhydride (12 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, and to this mixture was added isopropoxide (10 g.). The reaction mixture was refluxed (bath temp. 120-25°) for 6½ hrs. and then the benzene was fractionated. After removing isopropyl butyrateⁿ under vacuum, a colorless liquid slowly started distilling. When about 1 g. had been collected, the receiver was changed. At about 180° bath, a colorless liquid slowly distilled at 101-102°/0.5mm. [Found: Si, 9.05. (OPr)₂-Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 8.75%].

(c). *In Molar Ratio of 1:3.*—Butyric anhydride (19 g.) was added to silicon isopropoxide (10 g.) in a 100 ml flask to which was added benzene (15 g.). The mixture was refluxed under a column for about 16 hrs. (bath temp. 120-30°). After fractionating benzene over the column and removing isopropyl butyrateⁿ in the pump, a colorless liquid (7 g.) was obtained at 103-105°/0.2-0.3 mm. [Found: Si, 8.76; OPrⁱ, 36.56. (OPr)₂-Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 8.75; OPrⁱ, 36.86%].

(d). *In Molar Ratio of 1:4.*—Butyric anhydride (24 g.) was added to silicon isopropoxide (10 g.) in a 150 ml flask to which was added benzene (14 g.). The mixture was refluxed under a column for about 21 hrs. (bath temp. 120-25°). After fractionating benzene over the column and removing isopropyl butyrateⁿ in the pump of a very low bath, a colorless liquid (7 g.) was obtained at 121.5°/1.5mm at 210-20° bath. [Found: Si, 8.69; OPrⁱ, 36.76. (OPr)₂-Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 8.75; OPrⁱ, 36.86%].

Reactions between Silicon Butoxideⁿ and Acetic Anhydride

(a). *In Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—Acetic anhydride (1.5 g.) was added to benzene (4.7 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, to which was added silicon butoxideⁿ (5 g.). No heat was evolved and no solid separated. The mixture was refluxed for 2½ hrs. (bath temp. 110-15°). Benzene and butylⁿ acetate (b.p. 126°) were removed under pump at a very low bath. The ester could not be trapped even by using a powerful freezing mixture. When bath was raised to 200°, a colorless liquid (4 g.) slowly distilled at 166-68°/5-5.5 mm. [Found: C, 52.80; H, 9.00; Si, 9.31. (OBuⁿ)₃-Si(OOC.CH₃)₂ requires C, 54.86; H, 9.86; Si, 9.15%].

(b). *In Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—Acetic anhydride (3.0 g.) was added to benzene (5.2 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, to which was added silicon butoxideⁿ (4.4 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 2½ hrs. (bath temp. 130-40°). After removing benzene and the ester under vacuum, a colorless liquid (3 g.) slowly distilled at 134-35°/0.5-0.7 mm. [Found: Si, 9.69; M.W. (hexaneⁿ), 284.1. (OBuⁿ)₂-Si(OOC.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 9.59%; M.W., 292].

(c). *In Molar Ratio of 1:3.*—Acetic anhydride (2.5 g.) was added to benzene (6.0 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, to which was added silicon butoxideⁿ (2.6 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 6½ hrs. (bath temp. 118-20°). After removal of benzene and the ester under vacuum, a colorless liquid (1.8 g.) was obtained at 152-54°/3-4 mm. [Found: Si, 9.79. (OBuⁿ)₃-Si(OOC.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 9.59%].

(d). *In Molar Ratio of 1:4.*—To a mixture of acetic anhydride (7.1 g.) and benzene (9.0 g.) in a 50 ml flask was added silicon butoxideⁿ (6.0 g.) and the mixture refluxed* for 6 hrs. (bath temp. 115-20°). After removal of benzene and the ester in a pump, a colorless liquid (5 g.) was obtained at 121-22°/0.2 mm. [Found: Si, 9.82. (OBuⁿ)₂Si(OOC.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 9.59%].

Reactions between Silicon Butoxideⁿ and Butyric Anhydride.

(a). *In Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—To butyric anhydride (2.0 g.) and benzene (6.5 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon butoxideⁿ (4.0 g.). No heat was evolved and no solid separated. The mixture was left overnight and then refluxed for 2½ hrs. (bath temp. 115-20°). Benzene and butylⁿ butyrate (b.p. 165.7°/736 mm.) were removed under pump at 0.1-0.3 mm for 1½ hrs. at 140° bath. The liquid remaining was then distilled when a colorless liquid (2.5 g.) was obtained at 117-18°/0.5-0.6 mm. [Found: Si, 8.70. (OBuⁿ)₂Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃) requires Si, 8.38%].

(b). *In Molar Ratio of 1:4.*—To a mixture of butyric anhydride (5.5 g.) and benzene (6.4 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon butoxideⁿ (3.1 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 7 hrs. (bath temp. 115-20°). On removal of benzene and the ester under vacuum at room temperature, a colorless liquid (1.8 g.) slowly distilled at 119-20°/0.1-0.2 mm. [Found: Si, 8.14. (OBuⁿ)₂Si(OOC.CH₂.CH₂.CH₃)₂ requires Si, 8.05%].

Reactions between Silicon Amylⁿ Oxide and Acetic Anhydride

(a). *In Molar Ratio of 1:1.*—To acetic anhydride (1.42 g.) and benzene (4.21 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon amylⁿ oxide (4.64 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. (bath temp. 120-30°). Benzene and amylⁿ acetate (b.p. 148.4°/737 mm) were removed at 0.4-0.5 mm for 1½ hrs. at 85-90° bath. The contents were then distilled when a colorless liquid (3.0 g.) was obtained at 148-49°/0.05 mm. [Found: Si, 8.27. (C₅H₁₁O)₂Si(OOC.CH₃) requires Si, 8.05%].

(b). *In Molar Ratio of 1:2.*—To acetic anhydride (2.33 g.) and benzene (6.72 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon amylⁿ oxide (5.01 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 4½ hrs. (bath temp. 120-30°). After removal of benzene and the ester in vacuum, a colorless liquid (3.7 g.) distilled slowly at 150-52°/0.4 mm. [Found: Si, 8.76. (C₅H₁₁O)₂Si(O₂C.Me)₂ requires Si, 8.75%].

(c). *In Molar Ratio of 1:3.*—To acetic anhydride (3.0 g.) and benzene (6.0 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon amylⁿ oxide (4.0 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 5½ hrs. (bath temp. 115-20°) and then benzene and the ester were removed under vacuum at 100-10°. When the bath temperature was raised to 180°, a colorless liquid (2.5 g.) slowly distilled at 152°/0.4 mm. [Found: Si, 8.76. (C₅H₁₁O)₂Si(O₂C.Me)₂ requires Si, 8.75%].

Reactions between Silicon Amylⁿ Oxide and Propionic Anhydride

(a). *In 1:1 Ratio.*—To propionic anhydride (1.3 g.) and benzene (6.5 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon amylⁿ oxide (4.0 g.). No heat was evolved and no solid separat-

ed. The contents were refluxed for about 3 hrs. (bath temp. 110-20°). When benzene and amylⁿ propionate (b.p. 168.7°) had been removed in vacuum (using a cold trap), a colorless liquid (2.0 g.) slowly distilled at 146°/0.8 mm. [Found: Si, 7.91. (C₅H₁₁O)₃-Si(O₂C.Et) requires Si, 7.73%]. About 0.5 g. of the liquid could not be distilled.

(b) *In 1:4 Ratio.*—To propionic anhydride (5.5 g.) and benzene (7.0 g.), taken in a 50 ml flask, was added silicon amylⁿ oxide (4.0 g.). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hrs. (bath temp. 120-30°). On removal of benzene and the ester in vacuum (using a cold trap) at 0.3-0.4 mm for 2 hrs. at 120° bath, a colorless liquid (2.0 g.) distilled at 143-44°/0.2 mm. [Found: Si, 8.16. M.W. (in benzene), 344.4. (C₅H₁₁O)₃-Si(O₂C.Et)₂ requires Si, 8.04%; M.W., 348].

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